

Digital Co-Creation in Pandemic Conditions: Evaluation Survey

Final Report

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Background: IoTXchange

The IoTXchange project aimed to develop digitalization plans based on Internet of Things (IoT) solutions, with the purpose of increasing the quality of life in small and medium cities of the European Union. The first phase began in September 2019 and the second phase was completed in August 2022. The project was realised within the URBACT programme, an EU instrument for urban development with quite a wide scope. With a total budget of 744,166.92€, co-financed by the European Regional Development Fund in 70% to 85%, this project facilitated the exchange of experiences in a process of shared learning in order to enable all partners to address problems identified as common from new perspectives in an attempt to solve them in the future.

The Municipality of Fundão (Portugal) was the leader of this consortium which also included the municipalities of Razlog (Bulgaria), Dodoni (Greece), Nevers (France), Jelgava Local Municipality (Latvia), Ånge (Sweden) and Kežmarok (Slovakia) and the Finnish university Åbo Akademi University, whose Experience Lab collaborated with the town of Nykarleby in the project.

In the first phase of the project, a set of key issues that can be enhanced with IoT solutions were defined, and in the second phase local actors were involved through establishment of Local Action Groups, which had the task of elaborating Integrated Action Plans. These plans will be important tools for validating a strategy with an impact on the definition of territorial development priorities. Alongside creating the plans, the project partners piloted IoT solutions in service production in the shape of Small Scale Actions, designed to demonstrate and validate the benefits of IoT on a local level, and engaged in a number of bilateral visits and collaboration exchanges in order to learn from each other.

The Rationale For Evaluation

The conclusion of the first phase coincided with the outbreak of the Covid-19 pandemic, resulting in various degrees of lockdowns and restrictions on physical interaction, which meant that the second phase of the project had to be conducted mostly online. The transnational network meetings as well as the URBACT events were held online for two years, while some of the partners were able to arrange part of their activities in the “traditional” mode.

The rationale for evaluation was to capture the experience of going online without a thorough planning process, as it is valuable knowledge in the planning and implementation of similar processes in the future. Co-creation online was not a completely novel concept, but the impact of the forced digital transformation was still large enough to warrant an evaluation, since most actors in the project world expect at least some of the shift to become permanent – not due to health risks, but rather because of the need to find ecologically and economically sustainable modes of collaborating over distance.

Thus, the aim was not only to find out the experience of co-creation during the pandemic, but also to look forward and identify potential good practices as well as challenges to be faced when the work continues.

Survey Design

The evaluation survey was designed by Åbo Akademi University's Experience Lab, having the advantage of being the only academic partner in the URBACT programme, as well as working in the field of user experience and human centred design.

The themes and tools were planned together with the members of the network in order to align the methods with evaluation customs in the respective countries and build a common understanding of the topics we wanted to examine, to ensure that the survey felt relevant for the partners and the results could be of some use.

The survey consisted of two parts:

A semi-structured interview form based on seven themes to be discussed freely with members of the project partners' staff that had been engaged in running the local action groups, as well as optionally some key stakeholder for each partner, in online video interviews planned to last for approximately an hour. The interview form was designed in English and translated into Swedish, and the interviews were conducted in English with the exception of the municipality of Ånge (Swedish). The informants had been asked to prepare for the interview by selecting a specific process to examine; in most cases, the development of the integrated action plan was chosen, but in practice the small scale actions were also included. The interviews were recorded and transcribed, then qualitatively analysed.

An e-questionnaire directed at stakeholders of each partner, consisting of a set of questions with a choice of answers as well as fields for leaving comments, combined with sets of rating scales from two standard user experience questionnaires – the UEQ-S (Schrepp, Martin; Hinderks, Andreas; Thomaschewski, Jörg (2017): Design and Evaluation of a Short Version of the User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ-S)), consisting of eight pairs of words describing the users' experiences, and an abbreviation of Katrien Verleye's questionnaire for customer experience of co-creation (Verleye, 2015: "The co-creation experience from the customer perspective: its measurement and determinants"), with a rating of 13 statements about the experience on seven-graded scales. The questionnaire was designed to be filled out in 15 minutes. It was designed in English, and translated to Swedish (Ånge) and French (Nevers). The partners were asked to choose a number of stakeholders to fill out the questionnaire, and to remind them about the process in an introductory e-mail with a link to the survey. The questionnaire answers were translated into English and aggregated.

The data was collected and stored on Åbo Akademi University's servers, and anonymized for integrity purposes. The interview informants gave their consent to participate and to store the data through a written form or by oral consent at the start of the interviews. The identities of the questionnaire informants were not collected or recorded by ÅAU.

Some caveats should be considered when considering the results: The sample size N=25 was enough for getting the general picture of the experience, and enough background for a qualitative analysis – but not enough for drawing any statistical conclusions. Also, there were differences between the partners in framing the e-questionnaire – each did it in their own words, aligned with how the process was presented and how they worked in general. Cultural differences in giving feedback may also feature in the background.

Results: Summary

The full results are presented on pages 6 and onward in this document; the most important findings are presented in this section.

The project teams

The project partners' experiences were mostly positive, even though the work had been challenging at times. A typical reaction was that of an initial shock followed by adaptation – sometimes because there wasn't an alternative, but the general feeling was one of achievement. An important insight was that especially national and international cooperation became easier and more efficient when travelling was impossible – in the cases where the counterparts were known from before.

Among the downsides two things stood out; the increased dropout rate among stakeholders when the processes became more virtualised and the risk of digital fatigue if the work became a sequence of meetings on different platforms with different tools and logins.

Looking at the process, there was a general opinion that online collaboration is dependent on clear communication during and between meetings, to a much greater extent than working physically together. Online works for information, less so for communication.

The digital tools for visual collaboration, such as Miro, were a challenge, and creative tips and tricks were in demand – and in some cases, supporting the ULG members' motivation for virtual participation was difficult, and the dropout rates felt high. This was, however, not always related simply to the online factor. Another theme emerging was that the virtual mode of discussion didn't hamper the creativity, but in fact worked unexpectedly well and led to a more equal participation than physical meetings.

A common theme emerging was the realisation that online co-creation requires more planning and preparation from the organizer – and in cases of hybrid arrangements with some participants present and others online, this is especially important. The importance of a good facilitator was underlined – in some cases, the project partners' staff ran the meetings themselves, but others had brought in experts for the task.

We asked the project partners responsible for running the ULG processes for their best tips for success, and got a number of good advice – see pp 9-10 for the full list; here are some of the most underlined:

- Select good team members,
- keep it simple – participation, interaction, tools,
- choose good facilitators that lead, inspire and engage,
- keep the meetings short, take breaks, cause disruption, and
- make the schedule in advance – don't wait until the last minute.

Looking forward, most informants share the belief that hybrid and online are here to stay. This is mostly seen as a positive thing, as long as there still are moments of presence and social contact in the processes as well.

Also, it must be mentioned that any of the experiences and options extend from online co-creation to distance working in general – a phenomenon that was rather new to some partners, but clearly is on the rise. This also reflects the change of working conditions in general, not instigated but certainly accelerated by the pandemic, which means that a rethinking of how we work, collaborate and innovate is required from everyone involved. In some cases, new guidelines and principles are

already in development, and a change in working culture is expected to occur. This will also require training and practice – for arrangers as well as participants.

The stakeholders

Regarding the stakeholders: Starting from the background – how people had been working - the modes of working reflected the different approaches to lockdown and the differing circumstances. Three out of four had been working online, while two out of three had met physically. The general experience of work during the pandemic was reported positive by 19 out of 25, while the negatives were zero. Also, almost a third of the respondents had experienced a change in their attitude, perhaps reflecting a coming to terms with the advantages of working virtually. Many people reported efficiency gains from having to travel less – but in long processes, the importance of at least some face-to-face meetings was important as well.

Looking at the tools, 23 out of the 25 found them easy to use, and 24 respondents felt they added value to the process. All 25 felt that the co-creation process felt like a success, and 22 had learned new things such as daring to test new ways of working, improving their communication skills, as well as getting a better understanding of both the process and its subject – the Internet of Things.

A possible ambition from the stakeholders to please the local project manager cannot be totally discounted – and some of the open answers may be interpreted as “yes, but...” However, the overall positivity of the experience is fairly convincing. A follow-up could have been a more detailed “why” along the lines of q29 where the respondents gave explanations to their general experience of the pandemic.

We also asked the respondents to rate some of their experiences on a scale from 1 to 7 - where 1 = disagree completely, 4 = don't agree or disagree, and 7 = agree completely. The results were encouraging for the process leaders, as some of the statements (see full list on p 17) got very high ratings:

- It was a nice experience 6,04,
- It allowed me to keep up with new ideas and innovations 6,00,
- It enabled me to come up with new ideas 5,96,
- The interaction was pleasant 6,04.

Finally, when asked whether they would recommend others to participate in similar processes, all 25 respondents gave a positive answer. While the results aren't statistically significant, they nevertheless convey a positive message to those responsible for initiating and leading co-creative development work even in difficult conditions.

Reflections and support for designing online and hybrid co-creation

The overall results must be seen as encouraging for project and process leaders going hybrid or online – even allowing for the possibility that some positive answers may be influenced by the expectation of the situation being temporary and perhaps a feeling of surviving an ordeal together, there are building blocks for future success. There is a wide recognition of new possibilities having emerged, but alongside the old ones rather than instead of them.

Both partners and stakeholders recognized the need of a shared commitment to developing skills and practices, for organizers and participants alike. The skills in question concern both the tools and

methods – that will keep evolving – and the ability to choose the right combination of tools and practices for any given context.

A few other aspects of development in general also merit a mention when looking forward in this specific context:

- As the digital transformation advances at a rapid pace, new developments in fields such as the collection, processing and utilisation of data, solutions built on artificial intelligence and different kinds of visualisation technologies need to be monitored. Indeed, what we read into the concept of hybrid today may need to be reassessed in a very near future.
- Aspects of sustainability and inclusivity are crucial for societal development – and their consequences in specific contexts may not be obvious through yesterday's lenses. This is a field that should also be kept on the radar.
- And for any open social innovation process, making sure that the stakeholders are on board is an important starting point as well as a point of reference to check back to, making sure that new ideas and developments are spread in both directions – that there is a dialogue of development.

As an aid for planning and implementing hybrid and online processes, a manual with checklists before, during and after the processes has been compiled. It is based on the results of this evaluation and a similar process in the INTERREG OSIRIS project, as well as a set of interviews with innovation process leaders in a regional development project, *Digitala innovationsprocesser på distans*, internal workshops at Experience Lab focused on user centered design, and an inventory of online sources on the topic.

The guide is available on Experience Lab's website,

<https://explab.abo.fi/checklist-for-digital-innovation/>

or by contacting the author by e-mail: kimmo.rautanen@abo.fi

Results: Interviews with project partners:

Semi-structured thematic interviews were conducted with 1-3 people from each project partner that have been involved in the project; in all, seven interviews with 14 informants were held. Åbo Akademi University, the eighth project partner, wasn't interviewed since we conducted the evaluation.

0 Introduction

- **Where do you work? What do you work with?**
 - Municipalities, regional authorities, service providers
 - Project managers and coordinators, ICT, general and project administration, communication, procurement and legal matters
- **What tasks do you have?**
 - Project management, coordination, leading the project, managing the ULG, participating, providing the project with services or knowledge
- **Did your working conditions change during the pandemic?**
 - Some months from home, some mixed – half/half or similar, alternating to keep the office open but minimizing contact
 - A short period of mixed work, then back to the office as usual
 - Work from home for two years – all meetings online
 - Remote work became routine, it wasn't big before the pandemic but today it's different
 - The ULG worked in physical meetings but in smaller groups, max 10 people
 - First total lockdown, then combinations and variations – 2 or 3 days from home
 - Short period of total lockdown, then hybrid versions – and a presence at the municipality was needed
- **How did you experience the change?**
 - Sometimes there was more work at home – hard to keep track
 - Working from home was different – everyone have their own tasks but the flow of communication at the office is smoother
 - More participation in the digital mode – it became easy to join
 - The idea of European cooperation – meeting people and exchanging ideas and influences – suffered a bit. The trips would have been a kind of bonus for group members.
 - Workwise, if you get 80% by working online, why travel?
 - Remote work doesn't have extra stress anymore, and it saves time, but there is a risk of digital fatigue. You're expected to be on call day and night
 - It took some effort to adapt to circumstances
 - A shock at first, the first time that everyone worked from home was interesting, but then we got used to it and tired of it
 - The problem with working from home was the parts of the job that became difficult – informal exchanges, even printing documents

1 Background and goals

- **Can you describe the innovation or development process that you worked with during the pandemic**
 - The ULG process leading to an integrated action plan and/or small scale actions (for all partners)

- **The goal of the process?**
 - Formal: To create the IAP
 - But also to activate and engage people in general terms – see the possibilities of new technologies and start working for their introduction
 - And to bring together people from different sectors of governance – a city project instead of a department project
- **Which participants were involved?**
- **Where were they from?**
 - Local people mostly, the municipality, some politicians, NGOs and societies, some regional and national authorities, people from companies such as tech providers
 - The ULG size varied – from 5-6 to 20-30 people – but in some cases, the bigger groups were divided into smaller sub-groups to enable physical meetings and/or to enable a more efficient way of working online
 - There were also “core teams” of municipality people taking care of the overall process
- **Did you know the participants from before? Did they know each other?**
 - Some knew each other, or at least knew of each other, some did not
 - People working for the municipality mostly knew each other. Also, in the smaller groups that was one of the factors
- **How were the participants in the process chosen?**
 - Mostly contacted because of their expertise or who/what they represented, and to gather a group covering all bases – we contacted them
 - Some cases of open recruitment, through municipal/project facebook pages and such

2 The work process

- **What did the whole process look like? Was it only online or hybrid, that is, did you also meet physically at some point?**
 - Varied from online only to physical only, in some cases also with hybrid meetings. Some groups managed to start during an easier stage of the pandemic, some have only now gone to meeting physically
 - We tried some tools and techniques, but we didn’t have the proper time to make sure everyone learned them
 - Online “bodies were present, minds not as much”
- **How did you communicate between your meetings?**
 - E-mail, phone calls, corridor talk, in some cases no much or not at all
 - Creative minutes, or the facilitator summed up the progress so far before each meeting
 - e-mail worked fairly well, but we should have used online communication more
 - Communication between meetings took place only between experts and the core group
- **What worked well in the work process? Why?**
 - It was easy to participate from home – less time consuming, no travel – at least in principle
 - Online works well for information, but communication is more difficult
 - Some people found interaction, “raising hands” etcetera, difficult
 - The infrastructure worked well, even though we had feared it wouldn’t

- It was easier than we expected to create an IAP
- The facilitated small-group meetings, where people were chosen according to interest and competencies, allowed for creativity
- Brainstorming is different online/remote, but worked to some extent anyway.
- Keyword: Planning – scripted meetings
- Good facilitators – experts who knew both the topic and the methods
- Those participants who took the time to think
- **What didn't work so well? Why?**
 - The dropoff rates were quite high, more than 50%, and we weren't able to motivate people to stay in the process.
 - Disruption due to changes in staff – nobody to keep the process going and make sure everyone is involved
 - Some people didn't show up at all when we had to go online
 - "Monologues instead of dialogues"
 - The lack of informal dialogue, informal coffee break talk, or going for a drink and continuing the discussion after the meeting
 - We didn't entice people to think enough
 - **Was it possible to adjust the process if something didn't work?**
 - It was up to us, but we didn't change anything
 - I asked for feedback, but nobody wanted change
 - The meetings became shorter, people became more structured, but the informal exchange suffered – this was more self-adjusting
- **Were you able to control the work process yourself or was it given from the outside?**
 - In most cases yes
 - National or municipal covid restrictions forced us to rethink the process
 - URBACT methodology steers quite clearly
- **What did you think about this way of working?**
 - Preparations are important, facilitation if possible

3 Tools

- **What digital tools were used?**
 - Platforms: Zoom, Teams, Google Meet/Hangout, some open data (open source) tools
 - Visual co-creation: Miro, some Microsoft apps
 - Other: Menti, Google Forms
 - Presentation: Adobe acobat, powerpoint
 - We didn't really use any digital co-creation tools, we mailed materials to the participants beforehand, talked through the plans and drew pictures when we met up
- **Did you get to choose them yourself?**
 - Mostly yes. In some cases there were licenses that the municipality had bought that directed the choices, or there was a policy favouring open-source tools
 - URBACT promoted Miro through the eUniversity and in other ways.
 - Also, restrictions in sharing documents apply in some cases
- **What worked well? Why?**
 - In many cases, the tools that were used worked to satisfaction
- **What didn't work so well? Why?**
 - In some cases people just lost interest – perhaps due to being online

- A plan is non-tangible – not so easy to make engaging
- The open-source tools didn't really work
- Connections were sometimes an issue
- **Did the tools respond to your and the group's needs? If yes - describe what worked. If not, why not?**
 - In many cases yes – we had what we needed
 - A virtual whiteboard would have been nice – smoother than Miro for drawing
 - We used Miro with a “secretary” – the members gave instructions and watched online as the facilitator completed the board

4 Participation and creativity

- **If you think about what you described above - do you feel that all participants became involved in the process?**
 - Yes – and in some cases yes, but not all
 - We didn't ask too much of them
 - Yes – aided by a cameras on policy
 - Those who stuck with the process all the way were involved, but there was a big drop in participation when we switched to online
 - **If not - why?**
 - We would have needed some attraction or reward other than the pleasure of participation
 - Disruption due to people changing jobs, not being replaced
 - There may have been a drop-off due to the lack of a process leader
- **Did you feel that the way you worked gave room for creativity and “flow”? If so, what was it that did it? If not - why not?**
 - Not as much as in physical meetings – there are lots of cool activities for creative exercises that don't work online
 - There was a lot of creativity and there was room for it. Everyone's opinion counted because almost no-one was an expert – the threshold to contribute was low, and the spirit was good
 - Visionary work led to flow
 - Our facilitators were seasoned professionals who chose the methods but could also listen to the participants. They used design sprints as a tool
 - Yes – half the group were IT/IoT people, the other half saw the need for solutions, and they met
 - The process was mostly made up from conversation – but the ideas came up in that conversation
- **Were the participants allowed to influence the working method and process?**
 - No, we designed the process
 - In a way – the process was participant-led; they worked in depth came up with ideas in the small groups, that were then discussed in the bigger group

5 Results

- **If you think about the process you described - did you reach the goals that had been set?**
 - Yes – or yes, almost. All the IAP:s (primary goal) are underway
- **Were you satisfied with the results yourself? If yes - describe! If not, why not?**

- Maybe the process wasn't ideal – but the participants came up with a number of ideas
- As a stakeholder I am perhaps not satisfied, as a member of the project team I am
- The SSA was realised with one stakeholder only – the process wasn't very inclusive, and the other ideas were just thrown away
- We didn't really know what to expect – but it turned out good, and some spinoffs have occurred
- Some ideas have taken flight, others haven't (yet)
- The goals are quite challenging, but we'll see
- The SSA didn't quite succeed due to bad equipment (due to scarce resources)
- We reached the goals, and even found some new ones
- Satisfied with the result – but the group lost too many members on the way
- **What lessons did you learn from the process?**
 - We know more about needs, about what the process takes, and can plan better
 - A better understanding of IoT also gives food for thought
 - You need someone to keep up the dynamic of the group, especially when the topic is abstract and unclear at the start
 - URBACT is designed for city projects – dragging people out of their silos
 - We have started to develop the online teamwork culture
 - If people keep dropping out, we need to recruit differently, and perhaps along the way as well
- **Do you think that all participants understood and agreed with the goals that had been set and achieved?**
 - I believe they understood and agreed – at least their feedback is on target
 - **If not - why not?**

6 Ingredients In a good online development process

- **Think about the most effective parts of what you have described - what would you say is the reason why it was successful?**
 - Good manager + good team = good result
 - A good external facilitator makes the progress easier
 - Preparations – design according to the participants – and facilitation that creates a safe environment
 - Backing from the municipality – gave the strength to do it
 - Good communication yields good ideas
 - A given timetable supports concentration – but it is more difficult to control online
- **What are your three best pieces of advice for those who want to work creatively together in an online development process?**
 - Select good team members x3
 - Well-prepared meetings – and digital takes more than physical x2
 - Keep it simple – participation, interaction, tools x2
 - Good facilitators that lead, inspire and engage x2
 - Open the process to the community – not just the usual suspects, or at least open up some meetings
 - Make a good schedule – what are the right hours for the group members
 - Keep the meetings short, take breaks, cause disruption
 - Open discussion

- Direct communication
- Make the schedule in time – don't wait until the last minute
- Small groups for idea generation, big groups for discussion
- The mode of communication – people with communication skills, channels that are established
- Design to need
- Clear agenda
- Phones off, focus on
- Keep up the tempo – don't stretch the time between meetings
- Show the benefits of tech - educate
- **Do you have any horror stories of when it worked really badly? What was it that made it so bad?**
 - No answers

7 Digital innovation processes after the pandemic

- **How are you working right now? Has your organization drawn up guidelines?**
 - No specific guidelines in most cases – back to the old, by and large, but with a better understanding of working online and a growing number of people who have experienced it
 - And the demand for remote work and collaboration will grow when people get used to how easy it is
 - And more flexible procedures for those who want to/have to work from home
 - Remote meetings instead of “travelling to the capital” may become more frequent
 - No strategy – but a tested model that may pave the way for organizational reform
- **Do you have a model for working with this in the future? Tools, spaces?**
 - The digital has come to stay, but can't fully replace the physical
 - New models: Micromeetings with fixed scripts
 - Gamification
- **What does it require of your organization and you?**
 - Understanding of how people want to work
 - Better explanation and communication of aims and means at the start
 - Illustrating the gains of participation – perhaps small rewards?
 - Benchmarking of successful organisations and practices
 - We need to answer to “what's in it for me?”
 - The mindsets of work and home/leisure and how to separate them
 - The mindsets for how government works and how the offices work
 - Guidelines for working from home
 - Training in project leadership, virtual work
 - Courage to invite everyone and open up the processes
 - Getting used to collaborating and creating online
- **What does it require of your collaboration partners?**
 - Much the same as from us

Results: e-Questionnaire to Stakeholders

In all, 25 answers from stakeholders in seven of the eight participating cities (Kezmarok chose not to send out the survey). As the number of invitations sent out varied between the partners, with perhaps ten invitations on average, the answering rate is between 30 and 40%, which must be considered fair.

The volume of answers is big enough to warrant some general conclusions, as well as to pinpoint possible user experience related challenges, but it doesn't allow for very much individual case analysis for any of the partners. However, there are some general trends that apply for all or most, as well as some indications of differences.

Answers:

Background

1 Which country are you from?	N=25
Sweden	11
Latvia	4
Greece	1
Portugal	-
Finland	1
Slovakia	-
Bulgaria	5
France	3

2 How old are you?	
18-24	-
25-34	5
35-44	8
45-54	9
55-64	2
65-	1

3 What gender are you?	
Woman	13
Man	12
Non-binary	-
Prefer not to say	-

4 What is your role in the IoTXChange project?	
Member of project partner's staff	12
Stakeholder in regional innovation	5
Other	8

Questions about how you experienced the co-creation process in the project:

	Question:	Answers	
6	How have you been working during the co-creation process? Think of the whole process and all its parts.	Together with other people On my own In the office/workplace At home At events outside work or home	20 7 13 11 4
7	Comments	Physically in the office One meeting was held face-to-face (the very first, introductory), the rest were held remotely using MS Teams video-conferencing platform. Interacting with all the other members, brainstorming and take actions I have mostly worked from home and only on a few occasions in the office / workplace. On the occasions I have been in the office / workplace, we have been seen in small groups and kept our distance.	
8	Did the group meet physically?	Yes No	17 8
9	Did the group meet online?	Yes No	19 6
10	Did you understand what the aim of the process was?	Yes No	25 0
11	Comments	Yes the aim of the process was very clear from the beginning	
12	What work methods were used?	Discussion Co-creating with visual digital tools (e.g. shared boards/tables) Co-writing (e.g. shared documents) Individual assignments (e.g. creating documents on your own)	24 19 12 9
13	Comments	Almost all the above	

		We have more or less had a mix of all options at some stage of the process.	
14	What digital tools were used?	Teams Zoom Skype Mural Miro Discord e-mail Menti MS Office Digital whiteboard	
15	In your opinion, were the digital tools easy to use?	Yes No	23 1
16	Comments	Some less than others Miro is not that simple for a beginner not quite easy to begin with, but we got support Got a little messy when everyone "moved" across the page. The text became very small and if you enlarged it, you had to scroll a lot instead of seeing the whole thing.	
17	Do you think that the digital tools used added value to the process?	Yes No	24 0
18	Did the work feel successful?	Yes No	25 0
19	Comments	Got to result. yes in the sense that we produced something, but no in the sense that in my opinion, we could have done much better It was a team work and everyone has his opinion and the right to share it with the others Without digital tools, the process would have been less creative we had time to have a dialogue together	

		<p>What I see as successful are the discussions we had in the group and the ideas it aroused.</p> <p>New innovative ideas emerged and were discussed, several of which went ahead for implementation</p> <p>New knowledge / experiences in collaboration with others.</p> <p>We have made progress that has resulted in concrete solutions.</p>	
20	Did you learn new things in the process?	<p>Yes</p> <p>No</p>	<p>22</p> <p>3</p>
21	Comments	<p>Improvement of coordination and communication skills.</p> <p>I mostly worked as expert consultant.</p> <p>Automatization of processes in the areas not connected with my current job position</p> <p>that we do not need to meet physically for anything and everything, but that it remains necessary at least at some points of the project</p> <p>How technology can be used in many different cases and offer a very different value in each occasion</p> <p>Prepare digital presentations, use tools and plan to revitalize digital meetings</p> <p>on the conditions and agendas of other activities. About how to create goal images and action plans</p> <p>I have learned to dare to test new ways of working and thus not only focus on the finished result, but rather the success of at least having tested and done the best you could based on the conditions you have.</p> <p>Constructive digital working methods</p> <p>What IoT is and how it can actually be used to get added value / benefit.</p> <p>Preparation is perceived as more important for digital meetings than for physical meetings.</p> <p>To be able to participate and see results from other areas of activity</p> <p>the new forms of telecommunication. data processing.</p> <p>Understand the respective domains of each</p>	

22	Did you feel engaged in the work process?	Yes	24
		No	1
23	Comments	However, not enough time set aside.	
24	Did the group achieve the result that you aimed for?	Yes	23
		No	1
25	Comments	<p>Small scale PoC was deployed.</p> <p>Results are going to be observed in IAP document of the Municipality</p> <p>not enough resources to do so</p> <p>It became harder and harder to keep the group together as time went on. Especially as several participants disappeared along the way due to new jobs.</p> <p>P.g.a. corona, the project has been postponed. But otherwise we have worked out a good plan.</p> <p>Yes in part, remains the formatting of our project.</p>	
26	Did you feel that you could contribute to the result?	Yes	22
		No	3
27	Comments	Deployed the PoC	
28	What was your general experience of work during the pandemic?	Positive	19
		Negative	0
		Changed over time	7
29	Can you explain why?	<p>During the different periods of the pandemic, there was a lack of information, sometimes misinformation, which directly affected everyday life, including work processes.</p> <p>Adaptation process to all things and situations are required.</p> <p>Opportunity to save time resources and development of new skills</p> <p>first locked down was new, we discovered new ways of working, and that was an interesting experience overall, at least work wise</p> <p>for the other that followed, there was a lot of weariness, and longing to get a social life back, including work wise</p> <p>It was too sad to work from home alone for such a long time</p>	

	<p>Contributed to more harmony between work / family to be able to work from home. More efficient meetings. Higher productivity.</p> <p>flexible and efficient</p> <p>I am used to working in this way even before the pandemic. A big challenge was that everyone had different knowledge in working digitally or remotely, but together we have helped each other forward in the process and learned and developed during the journey.</p> <p>Efficient and reduced travel</p> <p>Time-saving and efficient folding was more positive than the negative parts that unfortunately come with teleworking</p> <p>The trips will be so much shorter :-)</p> <p>The change was forced and went quickly. After a while, everyone became more comfortable with digital meetings and then the work went better. From the beginning, it was difficult to create engagement among the participants in digital meetings.</p> <p>I have appreciated the flexibility</p> <p>I think I was effective during the pandemic, maybe even more effective than normal because I was less disturbed. However, human contact has been lacking and I find that it is difficult to get closer.</p>	
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Rating of the co-creation process from your viewpoint:

30 What was your experience of the process?

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7		
obstructive	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	supportive	5,60
complicated	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	easy	4,80
inefficient	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	efficient	5,72
clear	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	confusing	3,12
boring	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	exciting	5,80
not interesting	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	interesting	5,92
conventional	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	inventive	5,32
usual	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	leading edge	5,76

31 In a similar manner, choose your reaction to the following statements regarding the co-creation process – where 1 = disagree completely, 2 = disagree mostly, 3 = disagree to a certain extent, 4 = don't agree or disagree, 5 = agree to a certain extent, 6 = agree mostly, 7 = agree completely.

Statement		1	2	3	4	5	6	7
It was a nice experience	6,04						X	
It allowed me to keep up with new ideas and innovations	6,00						X	
It enabled me to come up with new ideas	5,96						X	
I could test my capabilities	5,68						X	
I gained a sense of accomplishment	5,52						X	
I gained new knowledge/expertise	5,84						X	
I met others with whom I share similar interests	5,60						X	
The interaction was pleasant	6,04						X	
I could make others aware of my knowledge and ideas	5,60						X	
I made a good impression on other people	5,04					X		
I had control over the quality	4,96					X		
I had an impact on the degree to which my preferences were met	5,28					X		
The risk of failure was limited	4,92					X		

32 Based on your experience of this process, would you recommend others to participate in similar co-creation processes?

Yes 25

No 0